

Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem nexus assessment: interactions between Scale, Circularity, Greening, and Digitalization in Urban Water Systems design

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Abstract

Urban Water Systems (UWSs) play a vital role in the Water–Energy–Food–Ecosystem (WEFE) nexus. This study explores how four design strategies—scale, circularity, greening, and digitalization—interact to influence urban metabolism flows, energy demand, and ecosystem services within hydrosocial systems. While these strategies are critical to sustainable UWSs, their synergies and trade-offs remain underexplored. Using a structured literature review and a systems approach, we mapped interdependencies among them, with an explicit focus on circular interventions—namely water reuse, resource recovery & reuse (R-RR), and water-cycle restoration (WCR). We outline an intervention typology matrix that can be operationalized for qualitative impact assessment in future case studies. The study highlights context-dependent outcomes and the need for an integrated design perspective to balance trade-offs, reduce environmental impacts, and maximize sustainability outcomes within the WEFE nexus.

Keywords

Urban Water System, Design, WEFE Nexus, Scale, Circularity, green-infrastructure, Hydrosocial Systems, systems approach.

INTRODUCTION

Emphasis on renaturing urban landscapes, circularity, decarbonization, and the promotion of smart cities in city design is part of the global and European agenda (Weerdmeester et al., 2023). To minimize unintended resource-management conflicts arising from siloed solutions (GIZ, 2020), resilient cities should pursue mitigation and adaptation strategies that account for cross-sectoral interlinkages among water, energy, and food security while improving the ecosystems that underpin these metabolic flows. These goals can be achieved when an integrated assessment applying the Water–Energy–Food–Ecosystem (WEFE) nexus is conducted before acting. Urban Water Systems (UWSs) are complex systems that import water from climate-dependent ecosystems or recirculate manufactured water via circular units, under the influence of urban metabolism and its cross flows within the WEFE nexus. UWSs establish interactions not only with the immediate urban environment but also with socio-economic flows, forming a hydrosocial system. The operational interface between UWS technical design and socio-institutional dynamics (e.g., behavioural, policy, organisational) gives rise to emergent hydrosocial functionalities—understood as the set of services, tasks, and processes the system must sustain under stress to remain effective (Fallon et al., 2022; Simonovic, 2021). The design of UWSs should therefore provide reliable water services while enhancing urban hydrosocial functionalities. Strategies that incorporate multiple water management scales, with varying levels of decentralization, produce repercussions on energy demand and the effectiveness of Water Management Units (WMUs). These units serve diverse purposes, including stormwater management, resource harvesting, and water reclamation. WMUs can adopt green or grey infrastructure, or a combination of both (Weerdmeester et al., 2023) and may be coupled with digital tools for monitoring and control—a transversal enabler rather than a stand-alone strategy (Zodrow et al., 2017). Thus, scale, circularity, greening, and digitalization operate as four interdependent design

strategies that underpin structural interventions for UWS resilience (**Figure 1**).

This research applies a system approach to evaluate potential interactions among four designing strategies that shape UWSs: Scale, Circularity, Greening, and Digitalization. The aim is to identify opportunities for maximizing synergies and minimizing trade-offs between them, and to enhance the ability of UWSs to cope with increasing water risks without harming ecosystems and increasing climate change phenomena.

Figure 1. Urban water cycle metabolism and interactions with other urban flows of the WEF Nexus.

METHODOLOGY

We conducted a structured literature review in Web of Science on UWS design strategies (scale, circularity, greening, digitalization) and WEF interlinkages. After title and abstract screening, we performed a full-text review of 128 articles, complemented with relevant standards and reports to cover operational and governance aspects. We then coded and categorized interventions as combinations of the four strategies with the support of an intervention typology matrix (**Figure 2**). We also defined a set of hydrosocial functionalities (e.g., storage, recovery/reuse, flood regulation, water-cycle restoration) to assess synergies and trade-offs across hydrosocial systems (**Figure 3**).

Matrix		Centralized	Decentralized
WATER REUSE	1 DIRECT POTABLE REUSE (DPR)	Centralized DPR Greening options: x Grey x Green-grey Green	Decentralized DPR Greening options: x Grey x Green-grey Green
	2 INDIRECT POTABLE REUSE (IPR)	Centralized IPR Greening options: Grey x Green-grey Green	Not applicable
	3 UNPLANNED POTABLE REUSE (UPR)	Centralized UPR Greening options: Grey x Green-grey Green	Not applicable
	4 NON-POTABLE REUSE (NPR)	Centralized NPR Greening options: x Grey x Green-grey Green	Decentralized NPR Greening options: x Grey x Green-grey x Green
RR-R	5 RESOURCE RECOVERY & REUSE (RR-R)	Centralized RR-R Greening options: x Grey x Green-grey Green	Decentralized RR-R Greening options: x Grey x Green-grey x Green
	6 WATER CYCLE RESTORATION (WCR)	Centralized WCR Greening options: Grey x Green-grey x Green	Decentralized WCR Greening options: x Grey x Green-grey x Green
		Digitalization	

Figure 2. Intervention matrix typology.

Figure 3. Methodology for the assessment of UWS design impacts on the WEFE nexus.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Circularity schemes present different infrastructure and energy demands related to treatment and transport (Khalkhali et al., 2021; Weerdmeester et al., 2023). In circular systems, treatment energy generally rises with stricter quality targets (which differ by circularity purpose), strengthening economies of scale in treatment; meanwhile, source separation (dual/multiple networks) increases conveyance and embodied-material costs. Therefore, maximizing the benefits of embedded water resources and minimizing energy costs of circularity require careful optimization of the scale of circular schemes, balancing treatment standards against separation and transport burdens. Scaling out and distributing green-blue facilities is key to achieving environmental amelioration across the urban fabric, encouraging decentralization. However, rising number of distributed smaller-scale facilities increases system complexity. Therefore, smart sensor networks can help manage this complexity through process automation and data-driven decision-making (Zodrow et al., 2017). Indeed, smart sensors networks allow remote control of WMUs, timely water quality monitoring, efficient irrigation during drought periods, and demand-side management to predict water use trends. It emerges, thus, that decentralization of UWSs may increase the need for digitalization, which at the same time can determine water systems to become more energy dependent. Green infrastructure in circular interventions provides stormwater control and water-cycle restoration, with ecosystem-service co-benefits and, when enabling resource recovery/reuse, reduced energy footprints.

The four design approaches impact the overall energy intensity of the UWSs and consequently the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. For example, direct potable reuse treatment tends to be more energy-demanding than indirect potable reuse, which in turn consumes more than non-potable reuse, with the WCR pathway presenting the lowest energy demand. Circular routes based on greening, usually related to the WCR, show the potential to establish GHG emissions offset through its storage. UWSs must ensure resource-efficient safe water, which means reducing system discharge and renaturing cities at adequate environmental costs.

Circular interventions display distinct synergy–trade-off patterns across hydrosocial functionalities (**Figure 4**). Decentralized systems tend to enhance social and ecological outcomes, whereas centralized ones favor technical and economic performance. Across circular pathways, WCR

performs best at smaller scales with higher degrees of greening; Water-reuse and RR-R gain in treatment economies of scale when centralized but pay more in conveyance, while decentralized schemes reduce transport losses and dilution. Digitalization supports these choices as a transversal enabler for monitoring, control, and data-driven learning and decision-making, and is particularly important given the added operational complexity of circular and decentralized configurations.

Figure 4. Radar chart of synergies and tradeoffs across hydrosocial functionalities.

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